

Larvicidal studies of chalcones and their derivatives

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Chalcone (1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one) is considered as the lead compound among all the chalcone type compounds used for the larvicidal studies, as it has the highest toxicity against the larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus*. 4-Phenylbut-3-en-2-one, where a methyl group replaces the phenyl group of chalcone, is less active than chalcone; but still has higher activity than other derived compounds except the oxime of the same compound, while 1,5-diphenylpenta-1,4-dien-3-one (in which the lengthening of the acyclic conjugated portion occurs) has almost no activity at 100 ppm at an interval of 24 h. ANOVA and CD values of the compounds show that larvicidal activity of 4-phenylbut-3-en-2-one and its oxime is greater than its phenylhydrazone, which has, however, higher activity than that of semicarbazone of 4-phenylbut-3-en-2-one. On the other hand the activities of 1,5-diphenylpenta-1,4-dien-3-one itself and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of chalcone and chalcone type compounds are almost nil at 100 ppm concentration at an interval of 24 h at $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The probable explanation of the fall of larvicidal activities of these compounds has been presented.

Chalcones are flavonoid type of compounds, which may be prepared by Claisen reaction. They also occur in various plants and have a range of biological impacts¹ such as antibacterial, anti-tumor, antifungal^{2,3}, antiviral⁴ and anti-plasmodial⁵ activities. A series of chalcones and their derived products have been synthesized and found to be novel potential anti-malarials, using both molecular modeling and *in vitro* test against both chloroquine sensitive and chloroquine resistant strains of *Plasmodium falciparum* and found to be active in nano molar range⁶. Besides those, chalcones and their acylhydrazides and related amides are found to be toxic against *Trypanosoma brucei*⁷. Lichochalcone-A, an oxygenated chalcone shows both anti-plasmodial^{8,9} and antileishmanial¹⁰ activities.

These significant bioactivities of chalcones and related products prompted us to study the larvicidal activities of some chalcone type compounds and their derived products against the larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus*, one of the intermediate hosts and vectors of filaria in human beings.

During the study of toxicity of piperine and similar types of carboxamides on houseflies, it was noticed that both piperine and piperidine of 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoic acid contain a methylenedioxyphenyl ring and same type of carboxamide group, but the difference is that piperine contains conjugated -CH=CH-CH=CH- with carboxamide, piperidine of 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoic acid contains no

such conjugation. Presence of such conjugation in the acyclic part increases the toxicity of piperine-pyrethrum solution than piperidine of 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoic acid-pyrethrum solution¹¹.

Previously, toxicity study of different chalcones against the larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus* was performed in our laboratory¹², which suggests that the chalcone, itself possesses high larvicidal activity but its activity decreases due to the introduction of different groups in the aromatic moieties or due to the lengthening of the conjugated portion^{12,13}, though in the case of piperine type of compounds it was not so¹¹. So chalcone may be considered as the lead compound. To confirm these results and also to study the activity of other products from chalcones we have synthesized 4-phenylbut-3-en-2-one and 1,5-diphenylpenta-1,4-dien-3-one in dilute alkali medium¹⁴ to determine their comparative larvicidal activity. Some of their derivatives have also been prepared¹⁴ so that a comparative larvicidal study of all the compounds synthesized may be performed of the 3rd instar larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus*.

Bioassay :

Following compounds were synthesized and used for the comparative study of larvicidal activity on the 3rd instar larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus* : Chalcone (1,3-diphenyl-

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2-propen-1-one) (1), benzalacetone (4-phenyl-but-3-en-2-one) (2), dibenzalacetone (1,5-diphenylpenta-1,4-dien-3-one) (3), 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of chalcone (4), 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of benzalacetone (5), 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of dibenzalacetone (6), phenylhydrazone of benzalacetone (7), phenylhydrazone of dibenzalacetone (8), semicarbazone of benzalacetone (9) and oxime of benzalacetone (10).

1	R = C ₆ H ₅	R ₁ = O
2	R = CH ₃	R ₁ = O
3	R = CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	R ₁ = O
4	R = C ₆ H ₅	R ₁ =
5	R = CH ₃	R ₁ =
6	R = CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	R ₁ =
7	R = CH ₃	R ₁ = N-NH-C ₆ H ₅
8	R = CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	R ₁ = N-NH-C ₆ H ₅
9	R = CH ₃	R ₁ = N-NH-CO-NH
10	R = CH ₃	R ₁ = N-O

Fig. 1

Outline of synthesis of compounds (1-10): Outline of the synthesis of compounds (1-10) is given below, because although these are compounds are known, some modification were made in their syntheses for better yield. We prepared chalcone type compounds (1-3) by Claisen reaction between different ketones and aldehydes in dilute alkali medium¹⁴. Compound (1) was prepared by reaction between benzaldehyde and acetophenone in alkali medium¹⁴, and it was further purified by dissolving it in benzene and then it was extracted with alumina whereby pure compound (1) was obtained which was employed in toxicity test. Compounds (2,3) were prepared by reaction between acetone and benzaldehyde in different proportions in dilute alkali medium¹⁴. In compound (2), methyl group replaced benzene ring adjacent to the carbonyl group of chalcone, while in compound (3), acyclic chain has been lengthened. The >C=O group of compounds (1-3) is converted to >C=N-X group (X= different substituents) by following the standard methods. In the case of compounds (4-6), >C=O

group is converted to >C=N-X group by boiling the methanolic solution of the carbonyl compound with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine and finally crystallization from suitable solvent¹⁴. In the case of compounds (7) and (8), the alcoholic solution of the compound (2) and solution of compound (3) in small volume of acetic acid were refluxed separately with aqueous solution of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and sodium acetate with continuous shaking, followed by recrystallisation of the respective crude products in dilute ethanol medium. Compound (9) was prepared from compound (2) similarly by the action of aqueous solution semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate to the alcoholic solution of the compound¹⁴, while compound (10) was prepared by refluxing the alcoholic solution of the compound (2) with aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and caustic soda¹⁴. Properties of these compounds are shown in Table 1. Melting points of the compounds were found to be the same as cited in literature^{14,15}.

Table 1. Properties of some chalcones and their derivatives

Comps.	Medium of crystallization	Colour	M.p. ^{14,15} (°C)	Yield (%)
1	Ethanol	Pale yellow	58	85.0
2	Petroleum ether (40-60°C)	Yellow	42	77.0
3	Ethyl acetate	Yellow	112	92.19
4	Aqueous ethanol	Orange	244 (d)	86.06
5	Aqueous ethanol	Reddish orange	227	92.72
6	Aqueous ethanol	Deep red	180	89.83
7	Aqueous ethanol	Yellow	156-157	86.24
8	Aqueous ethanol	Yellow	147	83.98
9	Aqueous ethanol	Yellow	187	91.97
10	Aqueous ethanol	White	116	88.43

Results and discussion

On the basis of toxicity tests, it was noticed that the compounds (mentioned earlier) could be divided into three categories, viz.

(i) Compound which exhibited 100 mortality of mosquito larvae at 100 ppm concentration after 24 h at 30 ± 2°C and that was chalcone [1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one] (1).

Variations of % mortality of this compound were measured at different concentrations and Probit Analysis was done for this compound as shown in Fig. 2. The LC₅₀ value was calculated and found to be 19.31 ppm.

(ii) Compounds, which showed no mortality of mosquito larvae at 100 ppm concentration after 24 h at 30 ± 2°C and those were (4), (6) and (8).

(iii) Compound which exhibited variation of % mortality of mosquito larvae at 100 ppm concentration after 24 h at 30 ± 2°C and those were (2), (3), (5), (7), (9) and (10).

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) calculations were done for the compounds and their toxicity are represented in the following ANOVA Table (Table 2).

Table 2. (ANOVA) Percent mortality of mosquito larvae for the compounds showing variation of toxicity at 100 ppm after 24 h	
Treatment	% Mortality
Benzalacetone [4-phenylbut-3-en-2-one] (2)	92.70 (74.32) ^a
Dibenzalacetone [1,5-diphenylpenta-1,4-dien-3-one] (3)	10.35 (18.72)
2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of benzalacetone (5)	2.11 (8.33)
Phenylhydrazone of benzalacetone (7)	62.03 (51.94)
Semicarbazone of benzalacetone (9)	21.00 (27.28)
Oxime of benzalacetone (10)	86.41 (68.36)
F value	54.45
	(significant at 1% level)
CD at 1%	16.10
CD at 5%	11.90

^aFigures in the parentheses represent the angular transformation.

From the calculations of ANOVA, CD (Critical difference) values were calculated for these compounds; CD at 1% level and 5% level were 16.10 and 11.90, respectively. From the CD values, the order of toxicity of these compounds can be determined and on the basis of CD and LC₅₀ values, a suitable larvicide may be selected depending upon the availability and economy.

Compounds (2) and (10) showed high percent mortality. So, variations of % mortality of these compound, were measured at different concentrations and Probit Analyses were done accordingly as shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively.

The LC₅₀ values for these two compounds were obtained by Probit Analysis and found to be 69.90 and 55.52 ppm, respectively.

On the basis of CD values, it was found that compound (2) and its oxime derivative (10) have same toxicity, which is greater than the toxicity of phenylhydrazone of the same compound. Again, phenylhydrazone of compound (2) i.e.

Fig. 2. Probit analysis of 1.

compound (7) has greater toxicity than semicarbazone of compound (2) i.e. compound (9). Compound, (3) and (5) may be considered inactive since their toxicity is less than minimum CD values.

Fig. 3. Probit analysis of 2.

Present toxicity studies show that LC₅₀ value of chalcone is 19.31 ppm. But compound (2) is less toxic than chalcone, which is also evident from the LC₅₀ value. So the replacement of the phenyl ring adjacent to the carbonyl group of chalcone by methyl group decreases the toxicity. But the lengthening of the conjugated portion of chalcone, as shown in compound (3), rapidly decreases the activity. So it has the same type of toxicity difference as previously studied in the case of carboxamide type of compounds¹¹. If the carbonyl group compound (2) is converted to >C=N-X group where X = OH, the toxicity remained almost the same. This may be the hydrogen bonding effect¹⁶ of =N-OH part. In the case of phenylhydrazone of compound (2), some toxicity is noticed but 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the same compound shows no toxicity due to the presence of two nitro groups in the phenyl ring. Being electron withdrawing in nature, nitro groups withdraw the electrons from =N-NH- and this may be the probable cause of fall of percent mortality of the larvae in the case of compounds (4-6).

Fig. 4. Probit analysis of 10.

Experimental

The samples were dried over P₂O₅/KOH at 80°C under reduced pressure for 24 h. Melting points of all the samples were taken in sulphuric acid bath in open capillaries and were uncorrected. Reagents used were of Sigma, Aldrich,

Fluka, E. Merck, B.D.H., S.D. or S.R.L. All the compounds were purified to A.R. grade before toxicity studies. Homogeneity of all the samples was tested by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel G coated plate of size $7.5 \pm 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ with different solvents as developer. The positions of the spots on the tlc plates were detected by UV light and in iodine chamber.

Method of bioassay :

Toxicity tests of the pure compounds (1-10) were performed on the 3rd instar larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus* in water medium. 0.5% of the alcoholic solution of each compound was added in thin stream with gentle stirring into the beaker containing 25 third instar mosquito larvae in water, so that the final concentration of the compound became 100 ppm at $32 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. In the similar fashion, same amount of alcohol was added to the control. Few drops of emulsifier were also added to maintain the uniformity of the concentration of the compound in the solution and similar addition was also done in control. Five replications were performed for each set. Percent mortality was calculated after 24 h. No mortality was observed in control. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) calculations were performed for those compounds, which were apparently found not to be equivalent. The order of toxicity was determined by Critical Difference (CD) values.

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References

1. E. C. Torres-Santos, D. L. Moreira, M. A. C. Kaplan, M. N.

Meirellis and B. Rossi-Bergmann, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1991, **43**, 1234.
 2. R. J. Anto, K. Sukumaran, G. Kuttan, M. N. Rao, V. Subbaraju and R. Kuttan, *Cancer Lett.*, 1995, **97**, 33.
 3. A. L. Okunade, C. D. Hufford, A. M. Clark and D. Lentz, *Phytother. Res.*, 1997, **11**, 142.
 4. B. K. Dewindt, K. van Emeran and K. Andries, *Antivir. Res.*, 1994, **25**, 67.
 5. A. Kharazmi, M. Chen, T. G. Theander and S. B. Christensen, *Ann. Trop. Med. Parasitol.*, 1997, **91**, S91.
 6. R. Li, G. L. Kenyon, F. E. Cohen, X. Chen, B. Gong, J. N. Dominguez, E. Davidson, G. Kurzban, R. E. Miller, E. O. Nuzum, et. al., *J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **38**, 5031.
 7. L. Troeberg, X. Chen, T. M. Flaherty, R. E. Morty, M. Cheng, H. Hua, C. Springer, J. H. McKerrow, G. L. Kenyon, J. D. Lonsdale-Eccles, T. H. Coetzer and F. E. Cohen, *Mol. Med.*, 2000, **6**, 660.
 8. M. Chen, T. G. Theander, S. B. Christensen, L. Hviid, L. Zhai and A. Kharazmi, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1994, **38**, 1450.
 9. L. Zhai, J. Blom, M. Chen, S. B. Christensen and A. Kharazmi, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1995, **39**, 2742.
 10. M. Chen, S. B. Christensen, L. Zhai, M. H. Rasmusen, T. G. Theander, S. Frokjaer, B. Steffansen, J. Davidsen and A. Kharazmi, *J. Infec. Dis.*, 1997, **176**, 1327.
 11. K. Harvill, A. Hartzell and M. Arthur, *Contribs. Boyce Thompson Inst.*, 1943, **13**, 87.
 12. B. P. Das, T. Roy Choudhury, G. K. Das, B. Choudhury and D. N. Chowdhury, *Environ. Ecol.*, 1995, **13**, 394.
 13. B. P. Das, D. N. Chowdhury, K. Ghosh (Das) and G. K. Das, *Environ. Ecol.*, 2002, **20**, 649.
 14. B. S. Furniss, A. J. Hannaford, V. Rogers, P. W. G. Smith and A. R. Tatchell, "Vogel's Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., ELBS/Longman, 1984.
 15. J. R. A. Pollock and R. Stevens (ed.) "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 4th ed., Eyre and Spottiswood (Publishers) Ltd., London, 1965.
 16. B. P. Das, D. N. Chowdhury, B. Choudhury, G. K. Das and T. Roy Choudhury, *J. Environ. Hlth.*, 1996, **38**, 81.